

Analysis of Relativistic Quantum Oscillator Equation Not Based on Local Energy

Conservation

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The quantum relativistic oscillator may be described by the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$(-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + mo^2) W = (E - .5kx^2)^2 W \quad ((1))$$

but due to difficulties with the x^4 term for large x leading to a lack of bound states, ((1)) has recently been replaced in the literature (1) by:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W - (mwx^2) W = (E^2 - mo^2)^2 W \quad ((2))$$

((2)) may be solved exactly to yield Hermite polynomial solutions multiplied by $\exp(-ax^2)$ just as in the nonrelativistic case, although "a" for the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases differ. In this note, we wish to analyse ((2)) as it does not yield a quantum averaged conservation of energy at each point x as the Schrodinger equation (and the Klein Gordon) do.

In a previous note (2), we suggested that ((1)) may be used to solve the relativistic oscillator problem between the classical turning points, but could be replaced at (or near) the turning points and out to +/- infinite with the Schrodinger equation as this region is nonrelativistic (the quantum averaged kinetic energy drops to 0).

Non-Relativistic Limit of $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W - (mwx^2) W = (E^2 - mo^2)^2 W$

To begin, it seems one may take the nonrelativistic limit of ((2)). In such a case:

$$(E^2 - mo^2)^2 = e^2 + 2mo e \text{ approx} = 2mo e \text{ where } E = mo + e$$

Then ((2)) immediately yields the Schrodinger equation as $w = \sqrt{k/m}$. Furthermore, the LHS of ((2)), when multiplied by $1/2mo$ is identical to the LHS of the Schrodinger equation. The right hand side of ((2)) is: constant W , where the constant differs from e , the nonrelativistic energy.

One may ask if there is a link between ((2)) and the Klein-Gordon equation ((1)). We argue that it seems one may take the nonrelativistic limit of ((1)) and then "create" ((2)). In the nonrelativistic limit, ((1)) becomes:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + mo^2 W = (e - V + mo^2)^2 W = mo^2 W + 2mo(e - V)W + (e - V)^2 W \quad ((3))$$

If one drops the last term on the RHS, one obtains the Schrodinger equation. Thus the term containing x^4 is a perturbation term in the nonrelativistic limit.

(It should also be noted that if one considers:

$$\sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2} + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

then one is not able to take the nonrelativistic limit of ((4)) for $V(x) = .5kx^2$ in the nonclassical large x region. The Schrodinger equation, however, is regularly used for the nonrelativistic quantum oscillator problem in this same region.)

If one examines ((3)), one may ask what changes are needed to create ((2)).

One need only replace the small $(e-V)^2W$ term with e^2W to obtain ((2)) and the x^4 disappears. Using $\frac{1}{2}(p^\dagger p + p p^\dagger)$ yields the LHS of ((2)) where $p \rightarrow p - imx$. One may solve ((2)) and find solutions of $\exp(-ax^2)$ multiplied by a Hermite polynomial, just as in the nonrelativistic case, although "a" differs.

Thus, ((2)) does not represent a quantum averaged energy conservation equation at each point x whereas ((1)) and the Schrodinger equation do. It should be kept in mind that a resonance occurs in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases, marked by $\exp(iEt)$ in the relativistic case and $\exp(iet)$ in the nonrelativistic.

Conservation of Energy and Wave Motion in Quantum Mechanics

It seems both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics are based on the idea of a quantum free particle being represented by $\exp(i(k_{rel}x - Et))$ and $\exp(i(k_{nonrel}x - et))$ respectively. In other words, there seem to be two channels in x space ($\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$) which are linked periodically and a similar situation in time. Furthermore, k_{rel} and E and k_{nonrel} and e satisfy a conservation of energy equation at each x . Imagine that one has a series of constant potential regions. Then, one might expect "plane waves" in each, but with different momenta. The conservation of energy would still apply and it seems that this conservation is linked to x .

In the case of a potential, it is argued that many different "waves" are stirred up (by the potential) and that an average is performed at each point x using $\exp(ikx)$ waves to try to obtain an overall "new" two channel object, namely $\text{Re}(W) + i \text{Im}(W)$, where W is the wavefunction. One may also obtain an average p^2 in a similar manner $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{Re}(W) - i \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{Im}(W)$. In both relativistic and nonrelativistic cases, one considers:

$$\langle p^2 \text{ quantum average} \rangle = \frac{\text{Sum over } p \quad p^2 f_p \exp(ipx)}{\text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \exp(ipx)}$$

For the relativistic case, p is the relativistic momentum and f_p a corresponding value, while for the nonrelativistic case, p is nonrelativistic and f_p a corresponding value. $V(x)$ itself seems like an average at each point x as one may take a Fourier transform of the potential. Thus, it seems unusual that ((2)) does not satisfy a conservation of energy equation at each point x based on quantum averages. In the nonrelativistic case, it does, so a physical explanation is needed for this difference at the relativistic level of ((2)).

Consider the Klein Gordon equation ((1)) and write W and V as Fourier series and group by $\exp(ipx)$. Then:

$$p^2 f_p = (e^2 + 2moe)f_p - (2mo - 2e) \sum_k V_k f(p-k) + \sum_{k,j} V_k V_j f(p-k-j) \quad ((5))$$

The last term on the RHS of ((5)) has the appearance of double scattering of a plane wave and the previous term, single scattering. In the nonrelativistic limit, the double scattering disappears and there remains only single scattering to form a resonance.

If one replaces W and V with Fourier series in ((2)) and collects terms for each $\exp(ipx)$, one obtains:

$$p^2 f_p - \sum_k V_k f(p-k) = (E^2 - mo^2) f_p \quad ((6))$$

Here, the nonrelativistic resonance seems to be retained with p_{nonrel} changing into p_{rel} , $f_{p_{nonrel}}$ changing into $f_{p_{rel}}$ and e changing into $(E^2 - mo^2)$.

Thus, the physics represented by ((1)) and ((2)) seems to be very different. In addition, it seems the Klein-Gordon equation ((1)) is used for potentials other than the oscillator. Thus, the single and double scattering picture of ((5)), it seems would apply to such potentials. If one has a potential for which $d/dx V(x)=0$ at x_a , one may expand it about x_a to obtain $V(x_a) + .25 x_a^2 (d/dx d/dx V \text{ at } x_a)$. This is an oscillator potential, thus if one uses ((2)) only single scattering would occur, but then both single and double scattering occur as one moves further away from x_a . This seems like a possible contradiction.

Meaning of $p+imx$

Mathematically, one may write: $p^2 + (imwx)^2 = \frac{1}{2}(p^\dagger p + pp^\dagger)$, but this raises the question as to the physical meaning of $imwx$. In previous notes, we have argued that in quantum mechanics there are two momenta (or related velocities). One is related to the square root of $-d/dx d/dx W/W$ for both relativistic and nonrelativistic cases, and the other to $-id/dx W/W$.

For a nonrelativistic oscillator ground state, $-id/dx W/W = i \sqrt{k/m} x$. For the ground state of ((2)), one finds $-id/dx W/W = x(\sqrt{k/mo} + 4 k/mo)$. Thus, both are linear in x and $\frac{1}{4} k/mo$ is a correction term in the nonrelativistic limit. Thus, $imwx$ is the nonrelativistic momentum flux and also the leading term of the relativistic flux. It may be noted that for the relativistic case:

$$\langle p \text{ quantum average} \rangle = -id/dx W/W = ix (E^2 - mo^2)$$

$$\text{and for the nonrelativistic: } \langle p \text{ quantum average} \rangle = -id/dx W/W = ix \ 2m \ e$$

This is a consequence of the form of ((2)), the RHS being of similar forms for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic situations. It is not clear why the relativistic equation ((2)) would be concerned with the nonrelativistic flux $im\omega x$.

Conclusion

In a previous note (2), we suggest the Klein Gordon equation ((1)) may be solved between the classical turning points and then joined with a Schrodinger equation solution which should hold near the endpoints to infinite. This avoids issues associated with $V(x)^2$ for the oscillator. In this note, we try to examine how ((2)) may be obtained from ((1)) and note that ((2)) does not preserve conservation of energy at each x while ((1)) and the Schrodinger equation do. We suggest that in a potential many “plane waves” are stirred up and one takes the average at each x to find a kind of average wave. One may also find a corresponding average p^2 . It seems that one would wish to impose conservation of energy at each point x given that $V(x)$ itself seems to be a kind of average. Finally, it seems that one needs a physical interpretation of $im\omega x$ in ((2)). In the nonrelativistic case, this is the momentum flux $-id/dxW/W$, while in the relativistic case, it is only the leading term of this flux which is again linear in x .

References

1. Rao, N. and Kagali, B. On the energy spectrum of the one-dimensional Klein-Gordon oscillator <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0704.1869.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Harmonic Oscillator and the Klein Gordon Equation (preprint, zenodo, 2019)